

Linking Pro-Social Motivation with Organizational Citizenship Behavior through Affective Commitment: Evidence from Female Entrepreneurs in Sub Saharan African Countries

Hassoumi Nouhou Nafissatou & Ye Chengang

Abstract

Previously, many explorations have been conducted on the mediating role of pro-social motivation (PSM) and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). However, theoretical arguments exist that affective commitment (AC) can mediate this relationship. This study is devised to fulfil the gap. It clarifies the relationship between (PSM) & (AC) and (OCB) in the light of women owner's businesses in Sub-Saharan African Countries (SSAC). Accordingly, online questionnaires have been conducted on 485 woman entrepreneurs from seven SSAC operated businesses in three sectors. A structural model has been used to test the relationships between variables. Confirmatory Factor Analysis was used through Descriptive Statistical Analysis using SEM software AMOS version 23. The results showed that PSM has a relationship with OCB. Second, it proves that PSM played a mediator role on AC and shows that AC & OCB mediate.

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About Author (s)

Hassoumi Nouhou Nafissatou (corresponding author), Business School, University of International Business and Economics (UIBE), Beijing, China.

Founder of Non-Government Organization "YAARANMOU"

Consultant & Counselor at "The African Countries Silk Road International Business Centre" Email: nouhou1000@yahoo.com

Professor Ye ChenGang, Business School, University of International Business and Economics (UIBE), Beijing, China.

Introduction

"Entrepreneurship" is seen as pursuing existing resources, with entrepreneurs hunting opportunities (**Krueger & Brazeal, 1994**). Therefore, female business owners were remarkable during the beginning of the 19 century, and African women have proudly contributed. It has been reported that around 61 per cent of women in Sub-Saharan Africa participate in the labour force, despite the enormous challenges they are facing. Consequently, the 1970 century has been a period during which a considerable number of scholars have dedicated their time to PSM (**De Dreu & Nauta, 2009, Korsgaard, Meglino, & Lester, 1997, Grant, Parker, & Collins, 2009**), and from the results of their studies; it is indicated that PSM practically and theoretically is a significant phenomenon because of it dramatically influences employees' work behaviours nonperformance. **Grant & Mayer (2009)**, although their study showed the necessity of the pro-social motivation (PSM) on the channel of investigation, as an effort of workforces who care roughly managing impressions towards and then becoming great citizens. On the other hand, some research showed that pro-social motivation reduced with positive self-concepts from starting to complacent **Grant & Wrzesniewski, (2010)**; others saw it as a factor that has a direct basis on employees toward a better task persistence, performance, and productivity (**Grant, 2008a**).

While organizational commitment has been a topic that has attracted scholars' attention for more than two decades, though the model developed by **Allen and Meyer (1990)**, organizational commitment (OC) has three (3) forms, and affective commitment (AC) is one of them, according to these researchers, AC is an extra reflection of identification and participation and expressive of employees to their organization. It might represent their loyalty resulting from an apparent responsibility to their organization and continuance commitment, grounded on the evident costs of leaving the organization. **Porter et al. (1976)** have reported that workers who exposed a lack of a positive attitude toward the team or the institute in the first week of work assignation were more likely to be quiet in their workplace.

Organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) has been an attractive issue since the 20 century. The majority of explorations that have been conducted in this regard were on the definition of the term (**Bateman & Organ, 1983; Moorman, 1991**). But later, some researchers have underway to investigate the dimension of OCB; neither OCB is an aid or guidance offered to colleagues, associates, clients, or the boss **Dennis W. Organ (2009)**. OCB is considered a different role for employees **Elizabeth Wolfe Morrison (1994)**. This exploration will also shed light on the mediator role of pro-social motivation leading to having a mediator role in the affective commitment of female owners of businesses in Sub-Saharan Africa countries from the results of the data analysis. Thus, in the case to achieve the purposes of this exploration, questionnaires following have been verified:

Does PMS play a mediating role in organizational citizenship behavior (OCB)?

Does pro-social motivation (PMS) play any role in affective commitment (AC)?

Does affective commitment (AC) link with organizational citizenship behavior (OCB)?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Brief Review on Females Entrepreneurs in Sub Saharan African countries (SSAC)

An enormous number of investigations have been done on African females engaged in economic labour activities. Therefore, a colossal number of challenges have been reported through a depth review of research papers on the issues of women entrepreneurial on the continent refer to the following outcome:

Relying on the result of a study reported by **Nziku (2013)** in Tanzania, 47 per cent of female owners of businesses have some difficulties finding some capital or collecting some appropriate information for the beginning stage of business. On the other hand, **Horrell and Krishnan (2007)** reported that lack of income inhibits women's garnering funds to start their businesses in Tanzania. Further, **Bekele and Worku (2008)**, in their study on women in Ethiopia, conclude that women-owned businesses were more likely to fail because they could not obtain financial support in loans. In addition, **Rwebangira (2000)** has reported some extra factors linked to the traditions concerning gender differences led credit discrimination and even more inhibition for women from inheriting lands that seek to be used as collateral for their banks loans. Women owners' businesses in SSAC, seeing as caregiver's lack of property possession managerial loads **Rwebangira (2000)**. According to the same source, accessing land or others property seems to be linked to their relationship with their partner's men, as wives or daughters. The most terrible matter is in the case of divorced or widowed, she might lose property rights only if she remarried her brother-in-law to keep the children and land according to the practice of clans on the continent. **Halkias et al. (2011)** investigated a group of Nigerian women owners of small businesses and highlighted their challenges: difficulty finding capital, generally low labour force participation, and low productivity levels. According to some researchers, of one the main difficulty for women entrepreneurs is control of the couple's cash income, which seems to be problematic concerning the opinion of men (**Rutashobya and Nchimbi 1999, p. 217**). Out of the listed above, poor infrastructure, lack of education, and lack of information are among cooperators. Hereafter operate more and less-profitable home-based commercial activities (**Vaa, 1989; Tripp, 1997**). In the case of gender discrimination, **Kinyanjui (2008)** reported that women owners of businesses are fighting to get out of the situation or find some solutions to turn it in their favour. Fortunately, (**Rutashobya et al. 2009; Kinyanjui 2008**) have pointed out some successful women entrepreneurs African context.

Pro-Social Motivation (PSM) & Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

The review of investigations (PSM) has been explored in countless fields such as organizational behavior, psychology, and especially organizational studies (**Grant & Berg, 2012**). **Castanheira, Chambel, Lopes, and Oliveira-Cruz, (2016)**, through their research of (PSM) motivation as a mediator amongst resources and work engagement, reported that high staff engagement might increase their levels of pro-social motivation. Furthermore, PSM inspires people to edge their behavior to help colleagues (**Arieli, Grant, & Sagiv, 2014**). In line with that, scholars such as (**Grant & Mayer, 2009; Grant & Sumanth, 2009**) have revealed the positive impact of pro-social motivation on organizational citizenship behavior OCB and their performance. According to some research, pro-social motivated employees uphold their tendency to help others **Lebel and Patil (2018)**. Consequently, other results of the investigation revealed that a person is prosocially motivated; he feels a rising swipe of positive mood or long-lasting energy, which leads them to create the most significant relations with colleagues or other individuals (**Abid et al., 2018**), maintaining that he or her show up OCB to other persons.

Pro-Social Motivation (PSM) & Affective Commitment (AC)

Ullah, I., Elahi, N. S., Abid, G., & Butt, M. U. (2020), through their investigation titled "The Impact of perceived organizational support and proactive personality on affective commitment: mediating role pro-social motivation. Using self-administered survey questionnaires and collecting the data from the service sector employees", in the case to investigate, the data were analyzed via Process Macros on an actual sample of 221. And the result has shown that pro-social motivation played an influential role in affective commitment.

Likewise, pro-social motivation is positively associated with affective commitment. Besides, the indirect effect of perceived organizational support and proactive personality on affective commitment through pro-social motivation is significant.

Mediating Role of Affective Commitment (AC) and Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

Meyer, Stanley, Herscovitch, & Topolnytsky, (2002) have reported that organizational commitment (OC) seems to be a decent analyst of the incidence of (OCB). **Meyer and Allen (1991, p.67)** have defined OC as "a psychological state that typifies the connection amongst the employee and their organization which might have implications on the decision to continue to be or a member or not of an organization" and as "an emotional promise bonding worker and the organization, and which making worker fewer likely voluntarily quiet the job." According to the same source, this psychological pledge possibly will take diverse forms. As reported by **Allen and Meyer (1990)**, OC has three states: affective commitment (AC), normative commitment (NC), and emotionally attached. **Meyer et al. (2002)** have conducted a meta-analysis to confirm organizational citizenship and affective commitment. Consequently, the average correlations between OC and OCB (average $r = .32$) and NC (average $r = .24$) are positive, but the calculation shows that commitment signifies no promise. The same investigation revealed that stress positively links organizational commitment and altruism ($r = .26$). On the other hand, studies have demonstrated a positive association between affective commitment (AC) and helping behavior & sportsmanship **Yoon & Suh, (2003)**. Researchers have not identified the mediator relationship between organizational dedication or affective commitment and OCB. So this paper has fixed amongst its objects to observe a positive correlation between affective commitment and organizational citizenship behavior (**Hypothesis 3**).

Relying on the literature on all variables relative to this research paper and the future research dimension of well-known scholars, we proposed the following research framework.

Figure 1: Pro-social motivation and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) model.

Research Objectives & Hypotheses

The objectives of this research are:

Firstly, to identify the mediating role of pro-social motivation related to females owning a business in Sub-Saharan African countries and its impacts. Secondly, we wanted to attract more researchers due to the lack of investigations in Africa, particularly Sub-Saharan African countries. Finally, we suggested some adequate solutions and recommendations which might assist these females in reducing the impacts of PSM on OCB. On the other hand, we urged assistance from managerial perspectives, which could help women owners of businesses, in general, deal with the influences of AC, PSM, and OCB for safety and a significant business environment.

The hypotheses of the investigation are:

- *Hypothesis 1: Pro-social motivation is positively related to OCB.*
- *Hypothesis 2: Pro-social motivation is positively associated with affective commitment.*
- *Hypothesis 3: Affective commitment is positively related to OCB.*

MATERIALS & METHODS

Research Design

The geographically scheming has been taken into account to accomplish adequate data collection. Thus, our target population is women owners of businesses from seven different SSA countries. Hence, our data was collected through an online questionnaire using Google Forms, and then we used the sampling technique requested by **(Millar & Dillman, 2011; Prakash et al., 2019)**. The sample size of this study has been calculated through the formula suggested by **(Millar & Dillman, 2011)**. According to the sample size asses to human dimensions, studies might be 400 responses with 95% sureness of interval and a margin of $\pm 5\%$ error. This investigation has a sample size of 485, which seems to be suitable for the demand.

Data Collection

First Phase: The adoption of survey questionnaires was prepared for this paper, designed through prior studies. But some of the questionnaires have been modified to develop an adequate French version. Questionnaires have been translated into the French language because there are five (5) countries where French is the official language amongst our targeting countries. A cover letter was linked with the survey instrument explaining a brief description of the investigation's purpose. Participants were guaranteed confidentiality and used only for academic exploration of the data.

Second Phase: We proceeded to the distribution of 900 questionnaires via email and phone call, and although the physical presence of the cooperators back in Africa (two times a week), due to the lack of internet and also because more than the majority of these females have a low level of education as shown the result of his survey.

Third Phase: After five (5) weeks of work, we completed the data collection. Nine hundred questionnaires were distributed, and 538 of them fully completed the survey. The results were related to demographic variables exposed amid the responses (23.71% is from Niger; followed by Nigeria with 22.88% and then Ivory Coast with 16.70%, Mali with 14.43%, and Benin, Ghana and Togo with 36 responses which represented 7.42% for each). The average age of these females was 30 years, while their sector of operation is Trade and wholesale, which is 80%. Among these women, the years of experience are more than 9 years (27%), and their education level is low, as indicated by more researchers concerned about females' education in Africa.

Measurements

Based upon previous explorations related to the variables of this paper, measurement items, although this study used a five-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagreed (1) to strongly agreed (5).

Regarding pro-social motivation (PSM), we have adopted our measurement instrument based on **Grant and Sumanth (2009)**. But, some sentences have been changed in the case to fulfil the French translation gaps. So, we have used the 6- items of the total.

Affective commitment (AC) (Mowday et al. (1979) have used three indicators to measure AC (i.e., "I find that this organization's values are very similar to my own."). And the average reliability of the scale was 0.78.

Organizational citizenship behavior (OCB), the five items of Podsakoff et al. (1990) to have measured the extra-role behavior of employees, have been adopted as the measurement with an average reliability coefficient of 0.93.

DATA ANALYSIS

Discriminant and Convergent Validities

Discriminant and convergent have been conducted to verify the validity of constructs variables. A confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) analysis was shown to test our hypotheses. For the second step of this part, we used a model comparison conducted to evaluate the structural models. As a result of CFA, see table 1, the discriminant and convergent analyses were joined together. The results confirmed the correlation amongst the investigation variables (**refer to the table below**).

To check discriminant validity, we have compared the square root of AVE scores to the corresponding variable correlational coefficients, as suggested by **Fornell and Larcker (1981)**. As a result of this founding, it was shown that the square root of AVE scores was significant and greater than the corresponding variable correlational coefficient values, as shown in Table 1. As a result, this study's discriminant validity is once again revealed. As the researcher employed self-reported measurements in the thesis, further supplementary tests were performed to confirm the standard method variance (CMV) effects, like the Harman evaluation. The results demonstrated that CMV is not the central subject of this study factor. At the same time, the entire loadings were loaded into EFA (exploratory factor analysis). Consequently, these findings confirmed that the constructs used in this study were valid enough to be used in additional studies to investigate postulated links.

This exploration used average variance extracted, commonly called (AVE), and composite reliability to verify convergent validity amongst our variables. Table 1 shows that all concept scores are based on shared values, indicating that this research has convergent validity. For example, all the factor loadings of the focal variables were higher than the required score of 0.70, proving all the constructs' convergent validities. In addition, the composite reliabilities, AVE, and Cronbach's alpha (α) values were higher than the required scores of 0.70, 0.50, and 0.70, respectively, which further prove this study's construct validities.

The result of **table 2** shows us the descriptive statistics of the entire variables are correlated, and the factor analysis and reliabilities are also linked. The mean and standard deviations both filled the standard deviation, as revealed in **table 2**. For example, pro-social motivation has a mean of 4.53; and SD .30, while affective commitment has shown us a mean of 4.61 with 0.40 as a standard deviation, and organizational citizenship behaviour comes up with a 4.52 mean 0.32 for SD. Relying on the results listed above, we assumed a significant statistical relationship between the mean scores and standard deviation. (**See Table 2 for more**). The sum of this part is clear evidence indicating the scales' constancy.

Table 1: Confirmatory factor analysis

Variable	Items #	Loadings	CR	AVE	α
Pro-social Motivation (PSM)			0.90	0.65	0.86
	PSM1	0.85			
	PSM2	0.79			
	PSM3	0.84			
	PSM4	0.71			
	PSM5	0.82			
Affective Commitment (AC)			0.90	0.60	0.84
	AC1	0.71			
	AC2	0.77			
	AC3	0.89			
	AC4	0.73			
	AC5	0.83			
	AC6	0.69			
Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)			0.91	0.64	0.89
	OCB1	0.75			
	OCB2	0.76			
	OCB3	0.85			
	OCB4	0.77			
	OCB5	0.81			
	OCB6	0.84			

Note: α = Cronbach's Alpha; CR = Composite Reliability; AVE = Average variance extracted.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics, correlations, and discriminant validity

Variables	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5	8	10	11
1 Age	5.07	1.29	1							
2 SoB	3.55	1.92	.04	1						
3 Exp	2.32	1.84	-.03	-.44**	1					
4 Education	3.68	1.93	.04	.33**	-.50**	1				
5 Nationality	4.66	1.89	.03	.09*	-.08	.09*	1			
8 PSM	4.53	0.30	-.06	-.21**	.16**	-.17**	.04	.80		
10 AC	4.61	0.40	-.04	.01	.001	-.02	.09*	.31**	.77	
11 OCB	4.72	0.32	-.01	-.13**	.14**	-.30**	.01	.29**	.42**	.80

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed), *Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). The bold values indicated square root of AVE.

Notes: SoB=Sector of Business Operation; Exp=Experiences of years; Ed= level of Education; Ny=Nationality; PSM=Prosocial Motivation; AC=Affective Commitment; OCB=Organizational Citizenship Behavior.

Control Variables

Four (4) variables have been used as control variables for this paper: age, experiences of years, level of education, and Nationality.

RESULTS

Through the use of means, standard deviations, and correlations, we have to assess the model fitness of our investigation. Then we have the procedure the overall model chi-square measure (X squared), goodness-of-fit index (GFI), comparative fit index (CFI), and the root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) are also used in this study. Universally, the values for GFI and CFI must be considered a better fit when they are above .90 (Bollen, 1989). The RMSEA value ought to be ideally .05. Nonetheless, a value up to .08 might also be reasonable, according to **Browne & Cudeck(1993)** suggestion. As shown in Table 2, the projected 7-factor model ($\chi^2/df = 2.27$, GFI = .92, CFI = 0.93, , RMSEA = .07) is the best fit; consequently, our suggestions were been supported for the distinctiveness of the study's constructs. Furthermore Table 1 shows descriptive statistics (i.e., mean, and standard deviation), correlations, and discriminant validity in respect of all the focal variables, The results further indicated positive correlation among pro-social motivation and affective commitment ($r = .31$, $p < .01$) and affective commitment and organizational citizenship behavior ($r = .42$, $p < .01$). In addition, the hypothesized model testing that allowed us to verify the mediating role of our variables was first assessed via performed SEM analysis to decide whether the hypotheses of this are not

supported. As shown in Figure 2, the first hypothesis of this paper stated that pro-social motivation has a positive influence on OCB has been accepted. The results of the SEM indicated that pro-social motivation is positively related to OCB ($\beta = .41, p < .001$). Hence, we have concluded that hypothesis 1 is supported. The second hypothesis of this paper presumed that pro-social motivation positively influences affective commitment. The results of the SEM revealed that pro-social motivation is positively linked with affective commitment ($\beta = .35, p < .001$). Henceforth, we have concluded that hypothesis 2 is supported. Thus, we want the hypothesis testing sector with the same methodology as the third hypothesis, which suggests that affective commitment mediates organizational citizenship behavior. Nevertheless, the outcome of the SEM results indicated that affective commitment is positively related to organizational citizenship behavior ($\beta = .50, p < .001$). Accordingly, mediating the relations between AC and OCB is also confirmed; therefore, our hypothesis 3 is also supported.

Figure 2: Results of structural equation modelling of the relationship among pro-social motivation, affective commitment, and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). * $P < .001$.**

DISCUSSION

The results of this investigation are authentic pieces of evidence to demonstrate the relation between PSM and OCB. As per the results, pro-social motivation is directly related to OCB. It is reliable to the hypothesis (H1) of this exploration and reported by some investigators (**Grant & Mayer, 2009; Grant & Sumanth, 2009; Rioux & Penner, 2001**). It demonstrates that employees are driven on a pro-social foundation to preserve their propensity to assist others, as Lebel and Patil (2018) reported. Henceforth, this outcome supports our **hypothesis (H1)**. The pro-social motivation of female owners of businesses in SSAC played a mediator role, or we might say it harmed their organizational citizenship behavior, as revealed in Table 1. Besides, hypothesis (H2) is supported in line with **Ullah, I., Elahi, N. S., Abid, G., & Butt, M. U. (2020)**. As per founding, pro-social motivation is negatively associated with AC due to the hypothesis testing into women participating in the economic growth in SSAC. Furthermore, the results reinforced the **hypothesis (H2)** that pro-social motivation acts as a mediator on AC. And affective commitment, which aligns with the **hypothesis (H3)**, has been supported as we have exceptions throughout the last part of our literature review.

THEORETICAL & PRACTICAL IMPLICATION

This exploration has practical & theoretical contributions. According to the investigation results, the investigation first needs to arrange training assemblies for these women to prepare and teach them how to enhance their pro-social motivation to grow their business and achieve an excellent OCB. Second, the African governments, in general, these investigated countries, should encourage these women to become familiar with the phenomenon mentioned above, via sensibilization or even by promoting those who are shown their interest in the training. These actions or assistance will increase women owners' business in SSAC and their sense of self-improvement, contributing significantly to long-run business. Third, the OCB behavior &

PSM have been studied in a diverse context; rare studies inspired women to run a business. So, the results of this investigation are unique via the demography situation of our targeting and the scope. The outcome of this study might contribute to the existing partial body of knowledge on the topic in general. The study results show that pro-social motivation is acting as a tool that might increase the AC of individuals, even though this data could not reflect the entire continent of Africa.

LIMITATIONS

We have investigated the mediator role of pro-social motivation and OCB from three (3) different sectors of female entrepreneurs of the above-listed Sub-Saharan African countries, which might impact their response rate. Finally, this investigation was limited only to the female entrepreneurs rather than including employees in the public sector, for example. And this study must also take into account others countries on the continent, such as Tanzania, Kenya, and South Africa.

FUTURE DIRECTION

This study offers a talented starting point for understanding the role of pro-social motivation in female organizations. The results throughout the data analysis confirmed to us how it contributes to situation change in terms of organizational citizenship behavior. Moreover, this investigation might consider psychological safety or organizational conflict in relationship work motivation.

CONCLUSION

This study proves the positive impact of pro-social motivation over OCB inside academic settings. Results exposed that PSM plays a mediator role in OCB. At the same time moment, pro-social motivation has impacted AC negatively. The study also indicates that women owners of businesses in Sub-Saharan African countries have boosted their desire to help others via their organizational citizenship behavior. The incapability to demonstrate organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) might be a presence during the period of their business. From data, vital and experienced businesswomen acquire a strong pro-social motivation toward economic growth. They might continue to operate a company with a significant and influential organizational citizenship behavior (OCB).

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